

OCCUPATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS, DURING A PERIOD OF CHANGE, IN THE ISRAELI LABOR MARKET

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Abstract: At a time when the world is undergoing significant changes in the world of employment, and robotics and computing are replacing the employee, we are aware of economic and social policies in various countries. This policy brings to light the social - economic - occupational characteristics that are tailored to each country. This article will try to examine the social occupational characteristics that the State of Israel is facing towards the third millennium.

Key Words: Labor Market, Globalization, Knowledge Economy, Economic – Social Characteristics.

CARACTERISTICI OCUPAȚIONALE ÎN PERIOADA DE SCHIMBARE PE PIAȚA MUNCII ISRAELIENE

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Rezumat: Într-o perioadă în care lumea trece prin schimbări semnificative pe piața muncii, iar robotica și informatica înlocuiesc angajatul, suntem conștienți de politicile economice și sociale din diferite țări. Această politică scoate în evidență caracteristicile socio-economice și ocupaționale, care sunt adaptate fiecărei țări. Acest articol va încerca să examineze caracteristicile ocupaționale sociale cu care se confruntă statul Israel către mileniul trei.

Cuvinte cheie: piața muncii, globalizare, economia cunoașterii, caracteristici economico-sociale.

1. Introduction

The Israeli labour market has improved markedly over the last decade, with the employment rate reaching historically high levels. While this partly reflects

remarkable progress for older workers due to the retirement age increase [13], more and more Haredim and Israeli-Arabs have also found jobs, though their employment rates remain low [15]. This problem is especially severe for Haredi men and Israeli-Arab women; indeed, progress has stalled for both groups. However, there is no guarantee that gains will continue much longer, since the stock of remaining inactive adults in these communities no doubt includes some of the most resistant to joining the labour market. Moreover, the labour market is still characterized by severe duality.

Moreover, job mobility towards high-productivity sectors is declining, which means that the probability that low-educated individuals will get jobs in high value-added, high-wage industries has decreased over time [12]. This is worrying; as such, industries are facing increasing skilled-labour shortages, undermining their growth and competitiveness. More than half of their companies recently reported difficulty filling jobs, particularly for engineers [21]. A special visa exists for skilled workers where there is no local expertise. Despite strong demand, the employment share of the high-tech sectors has remained stable around 12% of employment in the business sector for a decade, and they are said to lack more than 10 000 engineers [7]. Israeli-Arabs comprise only about 3% of the high-tech workforce, and Haredim are also under-represented.

2. The Financial Sectors

The situation is similar in many other sectors such as financial and professional services [5]. This reflects a number of difficulties and barriers including education and transportation issues, but also other obstacles such as language barriers, cultural and social norms – as well as insufficient inclusiveness of policies and program [4]. More needs to be done to improve the outcomes of these groups, not only in terms of employment, but also of wages and productivity. In addition; support programs for Israeli-Arab and Haredi entrepreneurs should also be introduced [1].

These measures should be complemented by better enforcement of existing anti-discrimination regulation. It may worthwhile using public procurement to increase incentives for firms to hire more Israeli-Arab and Haredi workers [9]. Gender equality also requires policy attention. The median gender wage gap, which is close to 22%, is higher than the OECD average.

This gap explained by lower working hours for women, but also by their choice of education field and industry [20]: women account for only about 25% of high-tech jobs [13] were related to the lack of childcare facilities, although corrective efforts are underway. Although expenditure on child-care and pre-school

education relative to GDP is slightly above the OECD average, it is comparatively lower when measured per child under four, given Israel's large share of this population age group. Increasing the number of subsidized crèche places for these children would foster labour force participation and would help women to pursue better careers, with higher wages [2]. This would be beneficial particularly for Arab women with low labour force participation [10] and Haredi women with large share of part-time work, who currently end up doing much unpaid work for their families. On the other hand, the existing eligibility for subsidized childcare facilities for Haredi families whose father is studying in a yeshiva is likely to be counterproductive for labour-market integration and takes available spaces from two-earner working families. Inequality and poverty in Israel remain high, despite some improvement resulting from the rising employment rate and recent measures to address the problem, such as increases in the minimum wage and in the **Earned Income Tax Credit (EITC)**. In recent years both gross and net income inequality have come down, returning the net measure to the levels seen in the early 2000s, implying important savings on transfer payments. Inequality, as measured by standard Gini coefficient, has decreased from 0.36 in 2011 to 0.34 in 2016. Nevertheless, the fact remains that average disposable income of the 10% richest households was 13.3 times that of the poorest, against a multiple of 9.4 for the average OECD country. Almost one-fifth of the population live in relative poverty the highest rate in the OECD. All age groups are affected, with a particularly heavy prevalence among children, but also among the elderly. Around half of Arabs and Haredim are poor, against 13.5% of non-Haredi Jews [20].

3. The Social disparities - poverty

One of the reasons for high poverty rates is the low level of social transfers (BoI, 2016c). While poverty measured before taxes and transfers is lower than in many other OECD countries, poverty after taxes and transfers is higher. As in other OECD countries, transfers do not include in-kind benefits such as free education and health-care services. Israeli social policy follows a "*welfare-to-work*" approach to tackling poverty in order to avoid measures that may harm work incentives among the Haredi, who value the time dedicated to religious studies, and the Arabs, who have cultural barriers to female employment [6]. Policy-makers are concerned that, although easing economic distress in the short term, higher transfers would perpetuate it in the long term by slowing the progress of their employment integration. The critical challenge they face is that many of those subject to (relative) poverty (specifically: Haredi men) do not want to work and are satisfied with a very low material standard of living. The Israeli government's strategy of

encouraging employment among previously nonworking families has met with substantial success. Moreover, the average real income of poor households has risen by 2.7-2.9% in the last six years, while the average real income of wealthier households has increased by only 2.2% [16]. Many households with only one provider and a persistent and widespread problem of poor job-related skills, it is just a first step whose benefits have been limited so far by the increase in the working-poor phenomenon. Many disadvantaged workers have been able to find jobs, but their families remain poor, since in most cases these jobs are low-paid. Indeed, the share of the working poor has risen in recent years and is internationally high. This is particularly true for the Haredim and Israeli-Arabs, for whom the increased number of breadwinners per family in the last decade has had only a limited impact on their poverty risks.

Therefore, the authorities should focus more on decreasing poverty among those in work. Improving the education system to enhance equity Extensive poverty and inequality in Israeli society are to a significant extent due to the wide dispersion of skills. Israel has one of the largest gaps between adults with outstanding competences and those with weak outcomes. The share of adults with top-notch numeracy skills is comparable to the OECD average, but the proportion of low-skilled adults is exceptionally high: for example, almost one-third of Israelis lack basic math's skills. These differences particularly pronounced between communities, which exacerbates already strong socio-economic divisions in Israeli society. Large wage gaps between Israeli-Arabs, Haredim, and the rest of the population for the most part explained by differences in skills (BoI, 2016d): the relation between wages and skills proficiency is relatively strong in Israel. Education plays a central role in the acquisition of skills at an early age and is a powerful lever to make society more inclusive. However, international assessments of Israeli students' outcomes (including PISA) show significant differences among students. Hebrew-speaking students have similar or better scores than the average OECD student, while Arabs lag behind. The share of poorly performing Arabic-speaking students was 45%, against 12% for Hebrew speakers. Almost no Arabic speakers reached the top performing cut-off. Particularly poor performance is found in the Bedouin community, whose children (below the age of 14) currently comprise almost one fifth of all Israeli-Arab children.

4. The Gaps in Education & Training Systems

This large dispersion in skills and students' outcomes is related to the segregated education system, which comprises four streams: one for Arabic speakers and three for the Hebrew-speaking communities, including Haredi, state-

religious and state schools. In the Arabic stream the instruction language is Arabic, and Hebrew is taught as an additional subject, while all teachers are Arabs. The situation in Haredi schools reflects an explicit choice of studying religious rather than secular subjects. Haredi boys aged 13 usually continue only with religious studies without secular core subjects, while girls spend much more time on secular subjects. These systemic features weaken skills formation in the Haredi and Israeli-Arab communities and contribute to the considerable inequality in socioeconomic outcomes. Since merging all the streams into a single system built around a common core curriculum is politically unrealistic, improving the education system requires building bridges between existing streams with the objective of raising the outcomes of low achievers, especially among Israeli-Arabs and Haredim. This will require higher public education spending, particularly on disadvantaged schools (see below). Despite significant increases in recent years, expenditures per student remain low. Moreover, budget allocations do not provide enough support for disadvantaged groups. Schools receive a basic budget that equally distributed according to student numbers and a grant (6% of the total budget) that reflects the school's socioeconomic profile. Additional financing comes from the municipalities, Better endowed local governments can provide 10-20 times higher funding per student than their less affluent counterparts, though the amounts involved are small (OECD, 2016d). Consequently, schools in disadvantaged areas comparatively underfunded, although the nature of this problem is different between Arab and Haredi schools Disadvantaged schools need much greater funding. Adjustments planned, and the five-year Economic and Development Plan for the Arab Sector, mentioned above, includes education measures, which if properly implemented, can help reduce these gaps. However, much more needed .

5. International Comparisons

For example, in Chile, a weighted voucher system allocates 50% higher resources for students from low socio-economic backgrounds [7] to provide extra teaching time or specialized learning materials. The authorities can also increase salaries for teachers working in disadvantaged schools. International experience suggests that much higher salaries are required to attract the best teachers to such institutions, but that financial incentives will be effective only if teachers given the means to be successful, such as by complementing higher wages with other incentives like smaller classes. Korea offers multiple incentives to candidates working in high-needs schools, including higher pay, smaller classes and additional credits towards future promotion [8]. A cost-efficient option that has had some success abroad is to set up a system allowing teachers to share good teaching

practices. Above all, there is a need to reduce the curricular differences between the education streams, which contribute to wide dispersion of average skills and educational outcomes among students from different communities. In the Arab stream, the government should keep trying to improve the teaching of Hebrew, as only 60% of Arabs have a good understanding of it. A better command of Hebrew would help Israeli-Arabs integrate into the job market [14]. While the government recognizes the problem and expanding the number of hours dedicated to teaching Hebrew in Arab schools. Ensuring substantial teaching of practical Hebrew and/or teaching some core subjects in Hebrew would be desirable. A complementary approach should include expanding pre-school education to children between zero and three and increasing their exposure to Hebrew.

Many voices were called It is necessary to improve vocational education and training; this is another problem that exacerbates skills differences is the low quality of the initial **Vocational Education and Training (VET) system**. Firms regularly express concern about VET graduates' lack of professional and technical skills (Musset et al., 2014). Particularly weak outcomes are found among students from the lower vocational track, which have much lower probabilities of qualifying for the Bagrut and higher dropout rates [10]. Moreover, studying on the lower VET track worsens graduates' labour market outcomes compared to those following the academic track [12] and relative rates of return to VET prior to military service, may be low over the long run (Hanushek et al., 2015). Many young people who pursue lower vocational tracks are poorly equipped for entry to the labour market. In this regard substantial components of work-based learning can be beneficial as it not only helps students to acquire practical skills, but also to develop key soft skills, such as work discipline, teamwork and problem-solving skills, which can be more effectively learnt in workplaces than in classrooms [3]. One-way forward is to expand apprenticeship and workplace-based learning, coordinating with industry partners. In Spain making workplace training mandatory in VET programs facilitated the transition of VET graduates to jobs [4].

For summary, Israel is at a crossroads. It has one of the lowest productivity levels and the highest poverty rates in the developed world. With roughly half of its children receiving a Third World education, future economic sustainability is not a foregone conclusion. On the other hand, the country's leading universities are excellent, and they are converging with the top American universities. The knowledge needed to raise Israel to viable economic trajectories exists within its borders. An extremely inadequate education system is unable to channel this knowledge effectively to the primary and secondary schools, which in turn limits the ability to enter quality institutions of higher learning. The important question is

what plan to bring a large number of creative learners and investors in Israel, *what is the Israel policy to improve the educational system? How Did Israel Become a Hub for Innovation? Does she will be innovation country with her employment stability?*

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